

Smart Energy Services to Improve the Energy Efficiency of the European Building Stock

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
BAC	Building Automation and Control
BACS	Building Automation and Control System
BEMS	Building Energy Management System
CEN	Comité Européen de Normalisation
CENELEC	Comité Européen de Normalisation Electrotechnique
CIA	Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability
DHW	Domestic hot water
DPP	Data protection and privacy
DR	Demand response
DSM	Demand Side Management
EE	Energy Efficiency
EEOS	Energy Efficiency Obligation Schemes
EN	European Standard
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Contracting
ESCO	Energy Saving Company
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute,
HBES	Home and Building Electronic Systems
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, Air Conditioning
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
M2M	Machine-to-Machine
P4P	Pay-for-performance
RER	Renewable Energy Ratio
ROI	Return on investment
SBT	Smart Building Technology
SDO	Service data object
SG-DPC	Smart Grid Data Protection Class
SGIS	Smart Grid Information Security
SGIMM	Smart Grid Interoperability Maturity Model

Acronym	Description
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
TBM	Technical Building Management
TBS	Technical Building System
TC	Technical Committees
TES	Tree Energy Solution
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The present report “Smart Energy Services to Improve the Energy Efficiency of the European Building Stock” of the SENSEI project is about defining data models and service interfaces for the smart services in the building stock.

The report presents a short overview on the Pay-for-performance (P4P) model framework used in SENSEI, which is a method for compensating energy efficiency services dependent on the performance targets achieved.

To define further requirements for the service interfaces and data models (SDOs) between the actors in a P4P scheme, corresponding standards are presented. References are made to the CEN and CENELEC standards, to the ISO TC's as well as to the IEC standards. Emphasis is placed on the standard EN 15232-1:2017, which comprises regulations for ‘*Energy performance of buildings - Impact of Building Automation, Controls and Building Management*’. In general, the elaborated standards are seen as the foundation for the requirements of services in the context of smart buildings. Particularly, the smart building technology mentioned in this report, including the specific services and data models, is increasingly dependent on interoperable interfaces, which can only be created with the help of standards.

Maturity models create an opportunity to assess and evaluate the readiness and development of smart services. This is particularly necessary to continuously improve the technologies adopted in the European building stock. On this basis, a deeper analysis is performed of the various methods, such as maturity models or Smart Grid Information Security (SGIS). As the aim of SENSEI is to design interoperable services and data models in the European smart building stock, a maturity model that identifies interoperability in the Smart Grid area is needed. In this sense, the SGIMM quantifies and evaluates the interoperability of different services and data models.

Information security assessment plays an increasingly important role in protecting services from attacks and for achieving long-term deployment. In SENSEI, different Smart Energy Services and data models were defined to improve the Energy Efficiency of the European Building Stock. Such Smart Grid services tend to span over diverse domains and zones and, thus pass through the information system. Due to these characteristics, it is necessary to classify and tag the data models in so called Smart Grid Data Protection Classes (SG-DPC). The assignment to the different classes is elaborated for the identification of suitable Service Levels in the Smart Grid

Information Security analysis as well as for the standards selection that is needed for each use case, component or actor.

The proposed design approach in this report, including standards, maturity models and information security methods contributes to the handling and implementation of smart services. All three aspects are imperative to reduce complexity and to integrate smart building technologies into the system in an interoperable and secure manner. Consequently, standards, maturity models and information and security are again emphasized in their necessity, but also in their application within the report. The outcomes from the above mentioned methodologies are used for deriving recommendations for standardisation bodies and the use of service data objects (SDOs) in the energy system.

The development of new technologies in the context of smart building stock, must examine new market models, use cases and relevant standards. Especially standards can reduce the technical complexity and integrate different systems into such a platform. The use cases around P4P should be elaborated and different meta-data should be added to implement SBTs. The analysis of the interfaces, which is based on the Maturity Models, can also reveal interoperability interfaces. The TRL is useful to check the technical and business side.

Finally, the deliverable summarizes the used methodological approach to develop interoperable Smart Energy Services, to improve energy efficiency of European building stock, as well as to draw conclusions for P4P programmes. The report provides key insights into the development of P4P programs for all participants in the energy market. For this purpose, standards are inevitable. Standards are not only used for the uniform transmission of data and information, they also create quality, trust and security for all market participants. However, technologies should not only be developed according to certain standards, but also reviewed with the help of maturity models. The aspect of IT security should also be emphasized, which is intended to protect data and information against attacks through various regulations and security methods. All in all, it appears that the development and introduction of new smart building technology is facing new challenging requirements, which are highlighted in this report. Finally, different recommendations are derived for handling these requirements for the development of new technologies in a complex and uncertain energy environment.

1 Introduction

The focus of this very deliverable in the context of the SENSEI project is to provide an overview of which standards apply to the interfaces of the existing services elaborated in the service catalogue. Service interfaces are later needed for the implementation on the platform. The service catalogue in SENSEI provides the functional point of view, but technical standards shall be used to implement those functions. As of now, there is a plethora of standards which could be used, therefore, the focus was set on a subset which has been already identified in various context and at European level. Typically, various standardisations bodies cover the interfaces between smart building and smart energy network. After a short review of the P4P model of the SENSEI project, a short introduction to those bodies and their standards is provided in the scope of this document within section 3. The following chapter 4 provides insights into the methods of maturity models, especially the Smart Grid Interoperability Model (SGIMM) and introduced the Smart Grid information security method (SGIS) as well as the related data protection classes (SGIS-DPC), focusing on the integration costs and security of the interfaces is given. After tailoring the methodological approach for SENSEI in chapter 5, an overview of the smart building technologies and the service data objects used in the project is provided in chapter 6. On this basis, chapter 7 shows how the methodological approach can be applied to the SENSEI models and the results. Subsequently, chapter 8 and 9 of the deliverable provide recommendations for SENSEI and the service data objects (SDOs) as well as future work. Finally, the results are consolidated in a conclusion.

2 The SENSEI P4P model – Short Overview

The concept of Pay-for-performance (P4P) is the key concept behind the developed SENSEI business models in the project [1]. In a P4P scheme for financing energy retrofitting projects, financial flows between the involved parties are linked to the actual – metered – and weather-normalised energy savings. This approach encourages long-term investment and transparent cash-flows (pay) in energy-efficient buildings by utilizing metering energy savings smart and getting a return on investment (ROI), based on proven and measured savings in the buildings under scope (performance) [1].

In the Pay-for-Performance (P4P) model, new technologies are introduced for achieving the aim of energy efficiency in the markets. The new stakeholders in the market have made investments

and allowed the energy efficiency to become a manageable procurable resource that can, additionally, contribute to bringing more flexibility into the (electric) grid [1].

Figure 1 P4P in SENSEI [1]

3 Listing of relevant standards

In order to pick the right standards for the services and interfaces, there is a huge set of Service Data Objects (SDOs) and results to pick from. In general, SDOs are technologies, which enable the access of heterogeneous data in a uniform scheme. The specification of SDOs define a Java-based programming architecture and API needed for data access [2]. SDOs established due to a collaboration between Oracle and IBM in 2004. The initial set of services was developed in work package 8 and is also documented in the deliverable. When selecting the basic technology, semantic and data model, and implementing the needed meaningful services for P4P, the following aspects have to be taken into account:

- Services for the buildings involved: those are already defined from a functional point of view
- Identified interfaces: the services were developed from a business perspective, therefore, the technical interfaces are important as well as the TRL of the basic technology implementing them.
- Standards related to the interfaces: while the services and interfaces could be implemented in a proprietary way, using technical standards to integrate large amounts of the same interfaces into the P4P systems in order to lower overall integration costs.
- Data Models provide the semantics as well as the serialization of the payload and data to be exchanged for technical processes.
- Protocols typically define the basic way to exchange the needed information and thus, are in the very scope of overall technical interoperability.
- Ontologies are so called controlled vocabulary that provide an understanding about how technical concepts are defined, related to each other and shall be understood.

Overall those factors drive the technical integration of the services provided in SENSEI. Mostly, technical standards shall be used. However, there is no such thing as a one-stop-shop for the technology needed here. Various SDOs must be evaluated and looked upon their work. A simple way to start was looking at the roadmaps of the big SDOs, like, e.g. at <https://mapping.iec.ch/#/maps>.

In the European Union, only standards developed by CEN, CENELEC and ETSI are recognized as European standards. For SENSEI, the following SDOs described in the next sections were looked upon with their results.

Relevant CEN standards:

CEN is the European Committee for Standardization within which CEN standards are prepared by the Technical Committees (TC's) [3]. They do not deal with electrical equipment neither telecommunication which is within the scope of CENELEC and ETSI. Within CEN TC 371 is the Program Committee on EPB standards. This TC 371 organizes this central coordination team in cooperation with the other relevant CEN TC's:

CEN TC 89, Thermal performance of buildings and building components

“Thermal performance of buildings and building components” is a standard in the area of energy performance buildings, including energy transfer through building components, as well as thermal insulation of installed equipment in buildings covering: Rules for the expressing relevant thermal properties and requirements, calculation and test methods, input data including climatic data and effects of moisture [4].

CEN TC 228, Heating systems in buildings

The standard “Heating systems in building” relates to all types of heating systems, including domestic hot water production, water based cooling emission and distribution systems in buildings and power generation systems in the environment of buildings [5].

CEN TC 156, Ventilation for buildings

The standard “Ventilation for buildings” relates to the terminology, testing and rating methods that dimensions, as well as serviceability of natural and mechanical ventilation systems and components for occupied buildings [6].

CEN TC 247, Controls for mechanical building services (EN 15232)

The standard “Controls for mechanical building services” relates to control and buildings management systems and services for residential and non-residential buildings. These standards contain definitions, requirements, functionality and test methods of building automation products and systems for automatic control of building services installations [7].

CEN TC 169, Light and lighting (EN 15193, prEN 17037)

The standard “Light and lightning” is responsible in the area of vision, photometry, and calorimetry, involving natural and man-made optical radiation over the UV, the visible and the IR regions of the spectrum, and application subjects covering all usages of light, indoors and outdoors, including environmental, energy and sustainability requirements and aesthetics and non-image forming biological aspects as well as lighting related information modelling systems [8].

Relevant CENELEC standards

CENELEC is the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization and is responsible for standardization in the Electrotechnical Engineering field. CENELEC, like CEN aims to remove

trade barriers in the European industry, as well as for consumers to facilitate global trading and welfare of citizens [9]. CENELEC cooperates with IEC at the International level, hence there are often mirror committees within CENELEC to what is developed within IEC. Consequently, the relevant TC's with work in progress can be found at IEC level.

CLC/TC 205 Home Building Electronic Systems

The standard CLC/TC 205 is responsible for Home and Building Electronic Systems (HBES). The standard ensures the integration of a wide spectrum of control applications and the control and management aspects of other applications within and between homes and buildings. This includes the gateways to various transmission media and public networks in view of all matters of EMC and electrical and functional safety [10].

Much are mirror committees of the IEC, therefore see also IEC operating at international level.

ETSI is the European Telecommunications Standards Institute, which produces standards for Information and Communications Technologies (ICT) including fixed, mobile, radio, converged, broadcast and internet technologies. An overview of important Smart Grid and building communication and interoperability standards can be found on their website [11].

A European Standard (EN) is a standard that has been adopted by at least one of the three recognized European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs): CEN, CENELEC or ETSI.

Relevant ISO TC's are:

Beyond Europe is also **the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) for non-electro-technical standards**. When an ISO document is released, countries have the right to republish the standard as a national adoption. When CEN adopts an ISO standard its reference becomes, e.g. EN-ISO-52000-1, and later on when a Member State adopts this e.g. DIN-EN-ISO. In the context of the ongoing review of EPB standards, many are expected to be published as EN & EN-ISO standards.

ISO/TC 163 Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment

The standard "ISO/TC 163" is responsible for Thermal performance and energy use in the built environment and part of the EPBD related standards. The standard relates to new and existing complete buildings, and the interaction with technical building systems. Likewise, the standard works for thermal insulation of installed equipment in buildings [12].

ISO/TC 205 Building environment design

The standard ISO/TC 205 is responsible for Building environment design, a.o. is responsible for ISO 16484 on Building Automation and Control (BACS). Hence, the standard relates to the design of new buildings and the retrofit of existing buildings intended for acceptable indoor environment, as well as practicable energy conservation and efficiency [13].

Relevant IEC standards

At the international level, the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) is the overarching organization of CENELEC being their European mirror. Within IEC the most relevant TCs from our view are:

IEC TC 8 System aspects of electrical energy supply

The standard “IEC TC 8” is responsible for systems aspects for electrical energy supply. The standard aims to assist the functioning of electricity supply systems to achieve the best balance between cost and quality for the users of electrical energy [14].

IEC TC 64 Electrical installations and protection against electric shock

The standard “IEC TC 64” is responsible for IEC 60364-8-1 ED2 on Energy Efficiency and IEC 60364-8-1 ED2 on Smart Low-Voltage Electrical Installations. The standard is used for electrical installations and protection against electric shocks from equipment, installations and systems without voltage limits [15].

IEC TC 69 Electrical power/energy transfer systems for electrically propelled road vehicles and industrial trucks

The standard “IEC TC 69” is responsible for Electric road vehicles and electric industrial trucks, amongst they take care of EV chargers. The standard is about electrical power/energy transfer systems for electrically propelled road vehicles, as well as industrial trucks using a rechargeable energy storage system (RESS). The standard shows potentials to relocate energy including conductive power/energy transfer, wireless power/energy transfer and battery swap [16].

IEC TC 57 covers the Smart Grid related connections of a building

The standards from the EC Mandate M/480 consist of two parts, whereas the first part is a normative part (for example with the template) and the second part is an informative part (for example containing proposals for default data). The following is a short description of the main standards. According to the Detailed Technical Rules, and in agreement with the mandate M/480 for each EPB-standard containing calculation procedures an accompanying spreadsheet

has been prepared to test and validate the calculation procedure. The spreadsheet also includes a tabulated overview of all output quantities (with references to the EPB module where it is intended to be used as input), all input quantities (with references to the EPB module or other source from where the data are available) and a fully worked example of the application (the calculation method between the set of input and output quantities) for validation and demonstration.

EN-ISO 52000-1:2017 Energy performance of buildings — Overarching EPB assessment – Part 1: General framework and procedures

The main output of this standard is the overall energy performance of a building or building part (e.g. building unit). In addition, there is a breakdown in partial energy performance, e.g. per energy service (heating, lighting, etc.), per building unit, per time interval (hour, month, etc.) and a breakdown in energy flows at different perimeters and e.g. delivered versus exported energy [17].

Depending on the application, all or some of the other standards related to the energy performance of buildings that cover other parts of the modular structure are needed (EPB standards). It introduces a modular structure to cover all aspects of the building energy balance and its subsystems, see the following table.

Table 1 EPB matrix [17]

Overarching		Building (as such)		Technical Building Systems									
	Descriptions		Descriptions	Descriptions	Heating	Cooling	Ventilation	Humidification	Dehumidification	Domestic Hot water	Lighting	Building automation & control	Electricity production
sub 1	M1	sub 1	M2	sub1	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11
1	General	1	General	1	General								
2	Common terms and definitions; symbols, units and subscripts	2	Building Energy Needs	2	Needs								
3	Applications	3	(Free) Indoor Conditions without Systems	3	Maximum Load and Power								
4	Ways to Express Energy Performance	4	Ways to Express Energy Performance	4	Ways to Express Energy Performance								
5	Building Functions and Building Boundaries	5	Heat Transfer by Transmission	5	Emission & control								
6	Building Occupancy and Operating Conditions	6	Heat Transfer by Infiltration and Ventilation	6	Distribution & control								
7	Aggregation of Energy Services and Energy Carriers	7	Internal Heat Gains	7	Storage & control								
8	Building Zoning	8	Solar Heat Gains	8	Generation & control								
9	Calculated Energy Performance	9	Building Dynamics (thermal mass)	9	Load dispatching and operating conditions								
10	Measured Energy Performance	10	Measured Energy Performance	10	Measured Energy Performance								
11	Inspection	11	Inspection	11	Inspection								
12	Ways to Express Indoor Comfort			12	BMS								
13	External Environment Conditions												
14	Economic Calculation												

In general, it is important to note that the standard defines system boundaries (the concept of perimeters and assessment boundary, as well as zoning) and amongst others also defines a Renewable Energy Ratio (RER) [17].

The contribution of BAC including technical building management (TBM) to the building energy performance is considered in the calculation procedure as the impact of all installed building automation and control functions (BAC functions) on the energy performance of the buildings.

It deals with the three characteristics:

- Control Accuracy (mainly used in emission and control modules M3-5, M3-4, M3-5)
- BAC Functions (mainly used in modules M3-5, M3-9, M9-5, M9-9)
- BAC Strategies (mainly used for M10-12)

The contribution of such a BAC function is taken into account by one of the following five approaches: time approach, set-point approach, direct approach, operating mode approach and correction coefficient approach. The application of one of the first two approaches - the time approach or the set-point approach - leads in general to a modification of the time programs and set-points, both coming from the module which defines the user profile (M1-6 Building Occupancy and operating conditions). Which approach is applied and how it is exactly done, is described in the EPB standard that is devoted to the module treating the BAC function (M10). For the BAC functions that are used in one of the EPB standards for the modules M3-5, M3-9, M9-5, M9-9, M10-5, M10-9, all five approaches are possible. Regarding the BAC functions, which are treated in M10-12, the first two approaches are applied.

Directly related to EPB, there are about 52 EN and/or ISO standards to define the calculation method. It can already be concluded that this update consists of a complex set of interrelated standards whose application of the proposed version is still in its infancy and it will be necessary to assess the extent to which the data contained therein can be applied [17].

Figure 2 Overview of applicable standards in the ongoing review of EPB [18]

EN 15232-1:2017 is the standard ‘Energy performance of buildings - Impact of Building Automation, Controls and Building Management.’ (Module M10)

This European Standard specifies [18]:

- A structured list of BACS and Technical Building Management (TBM) functions which have an impact on the energy performance of buildings;
- A method to define minimum requirements regarding BACS and TBM functions to be implemented in buildings of different complexities;
- A factor based method to get a first estimation of the impact of these functions on typical buildings;
- Detailed methods to assess the impact of these functions on a given building. These methods enable the impact of these functions in the calculations of energy performance ratings and indicators calculated by the relevant standards to be introduced.

The standard defines the following control functions [18]:

For heating control:

- ‘Emission control’, e.g. individual room temperature control with BACS including schedulers and presence detection can lower the general heat demand.
- ‘Control of distribution pumps in networks’, e.g. switching off circulation pumps when not required.
- ‘Heat generator control for combustion and district heating’, e.g. reducing the return temperature based on load forecasting to increase boiler efficiency by condensation.
- ‘Heat generator control for heat pump’, e.g. controlling the exit temperature base on load forecasting.
- ‘Heat pump control system’, e.g. inverter driven variable frequency compressor depending on the load.
- Other functions are ‘Sequencing of different heat generators’, ‘Thermal Energy Storage’ or ‘control of Thermo Active Building Systems (called TABS)’.

For domestic hot water (DHW) supply:

- Reduce stand by losses in hot water storage tank (if any) with automatic on/off control based on forecasted demand.
- Control of DHW pump (if any).

For cooling control:

Many of those functions are similar to heating (see EN 15232-1:2017).

- ‘Interlock between heating and cooling’ to avoid simultaneous heating and cooling.
- For air supply or ventilation (if any).
- Demand driver variable outside air supply.
- Heat recovery unit, icing protection.
- Free air night time cooling mechanical by automatic opening windows and/or operating the ventilation unit.
- Humidity controls (if any).

- Lighting controls: they can increase the building cooling demand or decrease the heating demand.
- Blind control: there are two requirements which are prevent overheating and reduce glare and therefore controls can be combined with HVAC and lighting.

The aim of the TBM system is to adapt easily to the user needs and therefore it shall be checked frequently. TBM functions are (see also EN 16947 with more details):

- Set point management, e.g. web operated heating/cooling temperature set points (20°C/26°C) with frequent resetting to default values where relevant.
- Run time management, e.g. predefined schedule (e.g. a night time set back temperature) with variable preconditions (e.g. no presence in the room).
- Manage local renewable sources or CHP to optimize own consumption and use of renewables.
- Control of Thermal Energy Storage of heat recovery (if available).
- Smart Grid integration.

Detect faults in the Technical Building System (TBS), for example:

- Read out alarms from the heat pump, gas boiler, and provide understandable building owner feedback and alarm logging.
- Continuous monitoring of SCOP (Seasonal Coefficient Of Performance – for heating) or SEER (Seasonal Energy Efficiency Ratio – for cooling) of a heat pump to verify maintenance needs (e.g. clogged heat exchanger, cooling fluid leakage).
- Regular checking sequence to verify the maximum power output of a heat pump or gas boiler to verify maintenance needs (e.g. contaminated gas burner, dirt on heat exchanger, valve errors, damage on pipe insulation, installation errors such as reverse connection of heat exchangers, correct control logic and set point of circulation pumps).
- Check the power consumption of the Air Handling Unit (e.g. increased power consumption due to clogged filter or air inlet/outlet, leakages in or clogged ventilation duct work, broken air dampers/fans).
- Reporting regarding energy consumption relative to indoor conditions:
- Show actual values and logged trends.

The standard also defines the four classes that pose specific requirements on the previous control functions. It contains a simplified calculation method based on BAC efficiency factors, for lighting reference is made to EN 15193.

The four classes of Building Automation Systems are:

- Class A: High energy performance building automation and control system (BACS) and technical building management (TBM).
- Class B: Advanced BACS and TBM.
- Class C: Standard BACS.
- Class D: Non energy efficient BACS.

For each class, minimum control system requirements are defined.

		Definition of classes								
		Residential				Non residential				
		D	C	B	A	D	C	B	A	
LIGHTING CONTROL										
Occupancy control										
0	Manual on/off switch									
1	Manual on/off switch + additional sweeping extinction signal									
2	Automatic detection Auto On / Dimmed									
3	Automatic detection Auto On / Auto Off									
4	Automatic detection Manual On / Dimmed									
5	Automatic detection Manual On / Auto Off									
Daylight control										
0	Manual									
1	Automatic									

Figure 3 Table on lighting controls defined in EN 15232 [18]

The simple method in the standard defines relations between building energy systems and BAC efficiency factors for different types of energy use, including lighting control, see Figure 2. These factors enable savings to be estimated. For a detailed calculation on the impact, the individual standards should be considered and therefore references to these related standards are included (e.g. EN 15193 for lighting) [18].

EN 16947-1:2017 Energy Performance of Buildings - Building Management System - Module M10-12 [19]

EN 16947-1:2017 is a new European Standard for addressing the TBM/BMS functions. This new standard covers several functions for the application of the building management system. Each function is represented by at least one calculation method. The functions are as follow:

- Function 1 – set points is meant for set point definition and set back.
- Function 2 – run time is intended for estimating run times.
- Function 3 – sequencing of generators is intended for estimating the sequential arrangement of different functions to be performed.
- Function 4 – local energy production and renewable energies is intended for managing local renewable energy sources and other local energy productions as CHP.
- Function 5 – heat recovery and heat shifting are intended for shifting thermal energy inside the building.
- Function 6 – Smart Grid is meant for interactions between building and any Smart Grid [19].

EN ISO 52016-1:2017 Energy performance of buildings -- Energy needs for heating and cooling, internal temperatures and sensible and latent heat loads -- Part 1: Calculation procedures [20].

This standard defines the building latent heat load using an hourly calculation interval. It describes an important parameter for modelling the impact of for example the BACS night time set back temperature function (EN or thermal storage in Smart Grids is the building time constant (τ)[hours]. It also contains a parameter to model the impact of the temperature control system ($\Delta\theta_{ctr}$), which is 0 for a perfect control system [20].

EN 15193-1: 2017 Energy performance of buildings - Energy requirements for lighting - Part 1: Specifications, Module M9 [21]

This standard deals with energy requirements for lighting and defines different lighting control systems (e.g. occupancy control type, type of daylight control, type of blinds control) and their impact on energy savings (e.g. occupancy factor (F_o), daylight factor (F_d)). It calculates the Lighting Energy Numeric Indicator for a building (LENI) in kWh/m²/y based on assumption for occupants' schedules (EN ISO 17772-1:2017). Background information to this standard is

documented in CEN/TR 15193-2: Energy performance of buildings — Energy requirements for lighting; Part 2: Explanation and justification of EN 15193-1, Module M9 [21].

CEN/TS 17165 “Lighting System Design Process” [22]

This document is developed in the frame of ENER Lot 37 and describes the key design considerations in the process for good quality, energy efficient and effective lighting systems in the tertiary sector [22].

ISO 17772-1:2017 Energy performance of buildings -- Indoor environmental quality - Part 1: Indoor environmental input parameters for the design and assessment of energy performance of buildings [23].

The standard contains indoor environmental input parameters for the design and assessment of energy performance of buildings. It deals also with occupants' schedules for energy calculations which can have important impact on energy calculations. Of course, apart from the assumptions, the real occupant behaviour will have similar impact. Advanced Building Automation and Control Systems (BACS) (EN 15232-1:2017) can include set point management which means that set points (e.g. illumination levels, comfort temperature, air quality, ...) can be redefined over the life time of the building when the task area, zone requirements or real user needs change. Usually however EPBD calculations [kWh/y/m²] are based on predefined occupants' schedules and comfort requirements and therefore they do not model properly the impact from set point management that adapt to changes in the user needs over its life time [23].

IEC 60364-8-1 ED2 Low-voltage electrical installations - Part 8-1: Energy efficiency [24]

This standard introduces requirements and advices for the design or refurbishing of an electrical installation with regards to electrical energy efficiency. It proposes a number of various electrical energy efficiency measures in all low voltage electrical installations as given in the scope of IEC 60364 from the origin of the installation including power supply, up to and including current-using-equipment. Amongst others it describes methods to decrease losses in electrical cables and transformers. [24]

IEC 60364-8-2 ED2 Low-voltage electrical installations - Part 8-2: Prosumer Low-Voltage Electrical Installations [25]

This standard is still under development. The standard provides additional requirements, measures and recommendations for design, erection and verification of low voltage installations that include local production and storage. The standard defines therefore how electrical installation requirements should be conceived to be future proof, without infrastructure lock-in

effects, could be useful for a technical installation service to check preconditions for local production and storage (however to be confirmed when the standard becomes available) [25].

IEC PT 60364-8-3 Low-voltage electrical installation - Part 8-3: Evolutions of Electrical Installations [26]

This standard is still under development. This standard provides requirements and recommendations to users and facility managers or similar of low-voltage electrical installations to operate their electrical installations as Prosumer's Electrical Installation. These requirements and recommendations cover safety and proper functioning [26].

IEC TS 62950 ED1 "Household and similar electrical appliances - Specifying smart capabilities of appliances and devices - General aspects" [27]

This new standard is intended to develop the common architecture which applies widely to different use cases and appliance types, and the principles of measuring smart performance within the context of the common architecture. The standard is in the Draft Technical Specification (DTS) stage and is expected to be published in a second edition in 2022. The focus of the standard is on smart capabilities for interoperability with Smart Grids [27].

IEC TS 62898-1:2017 on "Microgrids - Part 1: Guidelines for microgrid projects planning and specification" [28]

The standard provides guidelines for microgrid projects planning and specification. Microgrids considered in this document are alternating current (AC) electrical systems. This document covers the following areas:

- microgrid application, resource analysis, generation forecast, and load forecast;
- DER planning and microgrid power system planning;
- high level technical requirements for DER in microgrids, for microgrid connection to the distribution system, and for control, protection and communication systems;
- evaluation of microgrid projects. [28]

IEC 61727 Photovoltaic (PV) systems – Characteristics of the utility interface [29]

This standard applies to utility-interconnected photovoltaic (PV) power systems operating in parallel with the utility and utilizing static (solid-state) non-islanding inverters for the conversion of DC to AC. This document describes specific recommendations for systems rated at 10 kVA or less, such as may be utilized on individual residences single or three phases. This standard applies to interconnection with the low-voltage utility distribution system [29].

IEC 60364-7-712 Low-voltage electrical installations - Part 7-712: Requirements for special installations or locations - Solar photovoltaic (PV) power supply systems [30].

This part of IEC 60364 applies to the electrical installation of PV systems intended to supply all or part of an installation [30].

IEC 61851-1:2017 on “Electric vehicle conductive charging system - Part 1: General requirements” [31]

The aspects covered in this standard include:

- The characteristics and operating conditions of the EV supply equipment.
- the specification of the connection between the EV supply equipment and the EV.
- the requirements for electrical safety for the EV supply equipment. [31]

IEC 60364-7-722:2015 on “Requirements for special installations or locations - Supplies for electric vehicles” [32]

The standard applies to circuits intended to supply energy to electric vehicles, as well as circuits to feed electricity from electrical vehicle back into the supply network.

Amongst others it put additional requirements that has an impact in the electrical distribution board, protection devices and cabling within buildings to supply electrical vehicles. For example which and how Residual Current Devices that are needed [32].

IEC 62933-1 Electrical Energy Storage (EES) systems - Part 3-1: Planning and installation- General specifications [33]

This standard is still under development. This part of IEC 62933 is applicable to EES systems designed for grid connected indoor or outdoor installation and operation at a.c. or d.c. irrespective of voltage [33].

EN ISO 16484 is a series of 5 standards related to Building automation and control systems (BACS) [e.g.34]

The standard is about building automation and control systems (BACS) and consists of 5 parts. ISO 16484-1:2010 specifies guiding principles for project design and implementation and for the integration of other systems into the building automation and control systems (BACS). ISO 16484-2:2004 specifies the requirements for the hardware to perform the tasks within a building automation and control system (BACS). It provides the terms, definitions and abbreviations for the understanding of ISO 16484-2 and ISO 16484-3. ISO 16484-2:2004 relates only to physical

items/devices, i.e. devices for management functions, operator stations and other human system interface devices; controllers, automation stations and application specific controllers; field devices and their interfaces; cabling and interconnection of devices; engineering and commissioning tools. ISO 16484-3:2005 specifies the requirements for the overall functionality and engineering services to achieve building automation and control systems. It defines terms, which shall be used for specifications and it gives guidelines for the functional documentation of project/application specific systems. It provides a sample template for documentation of plant/application specific functions, called BACS points list. ISO 16484-5:2007 defines data communication services and protocols for computer equipment used for monitoring and control of heating, ventilation, air-conditioning and refrigeration (HVAC&R) and other building systems. It defines, in addition, an abstract, object-oriented representation of information communicated between such equipment, thereby facilitating the application and use of digital control technology in buildings. ISO 16484-6:2009 defines a standard method for verifying that an implementation of the BACnet protocol provides each capability claimed in its Protocol Implementation Conformance Statement (PICS) in conformance with the BACnet standard.

CEN 294, 'Communication systems for meters' provides a series of standards with respect to communication interfaces for systems with meters and remote reading of meters for all kind of fluids and energies distributed by network.

Based on the various technical standards evolving around the building, its flexibilities and communication link to the energy grid and network, the main aspect is the communication between systems in order to create digital processes for P4P communications [35].

Typically, one has to distinguish between various levels of interoperability, mostly four of a kind, which will be discussed in the next paragraphs. Assessing interoperability by metrics is not completely new in the context of the Smart Readiness Indicator. As early as in the 1980s, this has been defined as a problem by the EC¹. First, this was only treated as a problem from the perspective of team working on code for a common software or system towards a common goal (e.g. shared functionality). The focus was on easily integrating parts and components. Later, it became apparent that systems from various vendors with no common development unit would have to interact.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/eif_en

The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) introduced a Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), intelligence readiness indicator for buildings. It aims to measure the readiness of buildings for its usage of information and communication technologies and electronic systems that adapt the operation and supply of a building to the user needs. Likewise, it is an indicator to optimize the energy efficiency and overall performance of the buildings.

Interoperability is defined as the ability of one or more systems or elements to exchange information and to use the information that has been exchanged. One has typically to distinguish between four high level requirements for interoperability:

- **Technical interoperability**
- **Syntactic interoperability**
- **Semantic interoperability**
- **Organizational interoperability**

Technical interoperability in the context of the P4P services focuses on the hardware as well as software, plug-ins being compatible, the same protocols being used, platforms for M2M communications with back-end systems. As the system on a building is assessed at run-time this can typically be taken as given, since the system is operational at that time being.

Syntactic interoperability focuses on the data formats, while CSV based or XML based data still has the same format, parts may be missing in a payload or be optional. For the services in scope there might be information missing on some aspects of controls to be deployed. This shall not occur for a given, running system but the extension this will be a problem.

The dimension of **semantic interoperability** focuses on the interpretation of the data, meaning the same signal triggers a correct event or the data is interpreted the same by systems from different vendors. One specific taxonomy, which can be taken into account, is SARFE. The SAREF ontology presents a controlled vocabulary and concepts, which define semantics. For this deliverable, we have taken into account the main SAREF ontology as well as the Smart Appliances and SEP2 ontology [36].

The last dimension, **organizational interoperability** deals cross company, cross region and culture interpretation of the data, mostly, e.g. in the same context. Given the time before the GDPR, different organizations had different right and laws to treat personal data (e.g. with a data centre in the US). This harmonization of the system context leads to a better organizational interoperability in long term

In the scope of choosing standards for the P4P services in buildings to be implemented, many of the factors are too hard to be measured at inspection time by a non-system savvy technician from a third party. If interoperability metrics were to be introduced for the services in scope, a focus should therefore primarily be on the dimensions of technical and syntactical interoperability. A hypothetical analysis of such interoperability would require investigating multiple factors, such as: Standards explicitness

- Standards maturity
- Standards vendors supporting
- Standards feature coverage
- Standards profiles implemented
- Profile explicitness
- Profile coverage
- Profile extensions
- Profile documentation
- Products available supporting
- Product performance
- Supported platforms
- Conformance testing in place

As it is obvious from the extensive list presented here, assessing the interoperability of systems in a building environment and flexibility requires an elaborate assessment procedure in itself. After all, this contributes to a maintainable technical solution with better lifecycle costs.

4 Introduction to interfaces complexity metrics and security

The previous section has motivated the need for using technical standards as well as focusing on their functional requirements in terms of interoperability. However, dealing with standards alone can lead to islands of automation with little interoperability across organisations. In order to properly assess integration complexity and costs, so called interoperability maturity models exist. This is usually considered a non-technical requirement, as it strongly depends on the context and not on the performance of the individual solution. Next to the technical interoperability, security in terms of data protection is of high importance for the services. Within this section of the deliverable, we briefly introduce the Smart Grid Interoperability Model (SGIMM), a domain specific method to assess interoperability as well as its security. In addition to the introduction to maturity models, a smart grid security and privacy methods in terms of Smart Grid Information Security (SGIS) will also be discussed, including a particular focus on data protection classes (SGIS-DPC). By means of the listed standards and the methods of SGIMM and SGIS, the further methodical procedure in SENSEI can be further laid out.

4.1 SGIMM – Smart Grid Interoperability Maturity Model

A more specific type of a reference model that currently experiences an increased popularity is the maturity model. The term 'maturity' describes a "state of being complete, perfect or ready". In order to reach an intended state of maturity, a transformation process from an initial to a desired target stage needs to be pursued. Maturity models are employed to guide this transformation process. In essence, they represent an organizational tool used to develop more effective organizations or parts thereof. Maturity models are typically matrices spanned by the two dimensions capability areas and levels. Capability areas (also called "dimensions") describe different aspects of the object of maturity assessment. Each capability area is specified by a number of characteristics (practices, measures or activities) at each level. Levels in turn are archetypal states of maturity. Each level should have a set of distinct characteristics (practices, measures or activities per dimension) that are empirically testable [e.g. 37].

For designing and populating maturity models, different exploratory research methods and combinations of them are proposed. Commonly mentioned are literature analysis, Delphi and case studies, as well as focus groups. Quantitative methods are less frequently used for

constructing maturity, as these require a sound theoretical foundation. While the need for adaptability has been intensely discussed in the reference modelling discipline, it has hardly been addressed in the field of maturity modelling. However, given that the individual situation in which an organization resides in is an important influencing factor of maturity, it is also of high relevance for maturity models. For instance, some sources discovered that 73% of the organizations using the CMM model were stuck in level 1 during the period between 1987 and 1994. This was owed to the fact that the prescribed requirements of the area 'project management' were far too hard to be met. Certainly, the assessment model was too restrictive for that time period. However, since CMM was designed for rather large companies, it is also possible that the prescribed improvement activities were simply inefficient for small and medium sized firms (e.g., too much bureaucracy, missing financial possibilities for the realization). This brief example illustrates that – as with reference models - it is crucial for maturity models to clearly determine the situation characteristics for which the use of the model is permissible (e.g., scope and level of analysis, stakeholders) and/or to define adaptation mechanisms to extend the applicability of the maturity model.

The objective of a maturity model is to achieve interoperability within and between Smart Grid stakeholders. It focuses on organizational interoperability but it could however also be used for internal purposes of organizations. The three main objectives are described as follows:

- Maturity models offer help and guidance for improving interoperability at the community or national level
- They provide a means for assessing interoperability progress in the Smart Grid community
- They encourage an interoperability-aware culture with individual and shared roadmaps for improvement. Therefore, a maturity model must meet several requirements.

Looking deeper into the types of maturity models, the SGIMM was introduced in the introduction. As the aim of SENSEI is to design interoperable services and data models in the European smart building stock, a maturity model that identifies interoperability in the Smart Grid area is needed. In this sense, the SGIMM aims to quantify and evaluate the interoperability of, for example, different services. With regard to the so-called Interoperability Context Setting Framework, various dimensions and influencing factors could be combined into a requirements catalogue. On the level 1, the services have a minimum interfaces and are defined as the worst case, whereas the optimal characteristics are described as the best case and characteristics

between 2 and 4 as the average case. The SGIMM has different interoperability goals reaching from organizational, to informational and technical aims. Likewise, cross-cutting goals exist, such as configuration and evolution goals, operation and performance goals, as well as safety and security goals. Overall, the SGIMM is an encompassing model for assessing the interoperability of different systems or services in the smart grid.

4.2 M/490 - Smart Grid information security and privacy methods

The scope of the Smart Grid Information Security (SGIS) working group under the European Commission Smart Grid Mandate M/490 is to support European Smart Grid deployment. As quoted from the M/490 Mandate text: *'[...] It will answer the technical and organizational needs for sustainable 'state of the art' Smart Grid Information Security (SGIS), Data protection and privacy (DPP), enabling the collection, utilization, processing, storage, transmission and erasure of all information to be protected for all participating actors. This will enable Smart Grid services through a Smart Grid information and communication system that is inherently secure by design within the critical infrastructure of transmission and distribution networks, as well as within the connected properties (buildings, charging station – to the final nodes). This should be done in a way that is compatible with all relevant legal requirements, i.e. consumer data protection and privacy rights, metrology and daily business operations, and that is ensuring that rights of all consumers, including the vulnerable ones, are protected. [...]' [38].*

Cyber security requires an overall risk management approach where threats and measures are considered from technical, process and people point of view. The content presented by the group cannot provide a complete and definitive answer to the mandate's objective. The target of the work of the Smart Grid Information Security (SGIS) working group is to provide a high level guidance on how standards can be used to develop Smart Grid information security. In this light, it presents concepts and tools to help stakeholders to integrate information security into daily business [39].

One main aspect was to assess Smart Grid Information Security Levels (SGIS-SL) to the individual systems in the context of Smart Grids as well as to their interfaces and data being exchanged in the context of using an SGAM model. According to the EC M/490 mandate SGIS-SL served to bridge the gap between electrical grid operations as well as information security. It therefore focuses on the stability of the grid against external attacks. In general, five security levels have been defined between level 1 and level 5. While level 1 is the least critical to the energy system,

level 5 is the most critical to the energy system. The following Figure 4 shows the assessment for the SGIS-SL levels to the zones and the domains of the SGAM [39].

SGIS-SL HIGH LEVEL GUIDANCE*					ZONES	
3 – 4	3 – 4	3 – 4	2 – 3	2 – 3		MARKET
3 – 4	3 – 4	3 – 4	2 – 3	2 – 3		ENTREPRISE
3 – 4	5	3 -4	3	2 – 3		OPERATION
2 – 3	4	2	1 – 2	2		STATION
2 – 3	3	2	1 – 2	1		FIELD
2 - 3	2	2	1 - 2	1		PROCESSES
GENERATION	TRANSMISSION	DISTRIBUTION	DER	CUSTOMER		
DOMAINS						

Figure 4 SGIS level assigned to the individual SGAM domain/zone combination [39]

The illustration shows different vulnerabilities of the energy system. While attacks are less critical in the consumer area, an attack on the transmission networks can cause an enormous outage. Hence, the problem we face has very little to non-direct impact on the grid as a whole. The customer process level per se has very little large impact of disrupted. However, the closer the interfaces get towards the SCADA, as well as TSO and DSO communications, those interfaces become more interesting for malign intruders and third parties. Therefore, measures also have to be put in place if the number of participants and players in the P4P context grows [39].

4.3 SGIS- DPC

In SENSEI, different Smart Energy Services and data models were defined to improve the Energy Efficiency of the European Building Stock. Such Smart Grid services tend to span over diverse domains and zones and, thus pass through the information system. Due to these characteristics, it is necessary to classify and tag the data models in so called Smart Grid Data Protection Classes (SG-DPC). This helps to identify suitable SGIS-SL for the standards selection that is needed for each use case, component or actor. The emphasis here is also on confidentiality, integrity and availability from the CIA triad [39].

The SG-DPC classes can be distinguished in SG-DPC 1 “Personal Information” and SG-DPC 2 “System Information”, which are described in the Figure 6 below. Hence, it can be distinguished between system information as well as personal information in the context of the data being exchanged in P4P solutions and services. The first class describes domain independent protection needs used for privacy and domain specific protection, as well as the other class

relates to the protection needs of information assets handled in use cases/services. For each service at implementation time, the GDPR compliant solution must be evaluated [39].

SG-DPC 1 Personal Information
Sensitive Personal Information
Personal Information
De-personalized Pseudonym zed Personal information
No Personal information

SG-DPC 2 System Information
System Data (i.e. Firmware), Configuration Data, Customer Credentials, Private & Public Keys, Roles /Actor IDs
Governance & Reporting Information, Logging and Audit Information
Audit & Log required information
Information to administrate remotely
Information to operate remotely (Control signals)
Business Information
Measurement data

Figure 5 SGIS DPC classes 1 and 2 [39]

The table shown below represents the expected values for all use cases / SG-DPC in SGAM cell Domains for zone operation. However, specific use cases may differ from this. Therefore, the guidance may be more specific to use cases where the information assets and their Information Security Classification (SG-DPC) are known. The given values are mainly useful for interoperability causes. Thus, manufacturers can use the table as a guidance e.g. for exchanging equipment between different actors in the energy system. Especially for assessing certain risks that could arise, the SG-DPC can help to identify them and to provide information on how to diminish them [39].

		Example for Guidance SGIS-SL per SG-DPC					
SG-DPC 1 Personal Information	Sensitive Personal information	3-4	5	3-4	3	2-3	2-3
	Personal information	3-4	5	3-4	3	2-3	2-3
	De-personalized Pseudonymized Personal information	3-4	5	3-4	3	2-3	2-3
	No Personal information	3-4	5	3-4	3	2-3	2-3
SG-DPC 2 System Information	System Data (i.e. Firmware) Configuration Data, Customer Credentials Private & Public Keys Roles /Actor IDs	3-4	5	3-4	3	2-3	2-3
	Governance & Reporting Information Logging and Audit Information	3-4	5	3-4	3	2-3	2-3
	Audit & Log required information	3-4	5	3-4	3	2-3	2-3
	Information to administrate remotely	3-4	5	3-4	3	2-3	2-3
	Information to operate remotely (Control signals)	3-4	5	3-4	3	2-3	2-3
	Business Information	3-4	5	3-4	3	2-3	2-3
	Measurement data	3-4	5	3-4	3	2-3	2-3
Information assets used in Use Case to be classified to above 2 SG-Data Protection classes (both apply to one information asset) – not all will be used in a specific Use Case – e.g. Sensitive personal information may not be available in most use cases.		Generation	Transmission	Distribution	DER	Customer Site	Customer Internal Domains
		DOMAINS					

Zone Operation / all Layers

Figure 6 SGIS-SL vs. DPC [39]

In this context, also the GDPR must be taken into consideration. While the interfaces alone impose a threat mainly from being hacked, jammed, or spoofed, the data exchanged being exposed to third parties typically also imposes a risk as well as a legal requirement. The next section provides classes for the data protection of Smart Grid related data being exchanged [39].

5 Tailoring of the methods for SENSEI

Looking at the solution portfolio, it is apparent that the broad scope of standards from various domains, possible implementations as well as use cases of the services must be evaluated and defined in detail in the future. The previous sections have outlined the need for evaluation as well as initial starting point when implementing and assessing the P4P services which will be presented in the next chapter.

5.1 Smart Building Technologies in the P4P – services in scope overview

The so called Smart Building Technology (SBT) is according to the definition in the SENSEI project **an installation and technological instance that enhances a building's service portfolio through facilitating flexible and (more) efficient functionalities**. In concrete, SBT involves the conception, construction, commission, design as well as operation of building aiming to use the technology for optimizing the built environment. Such aims could be the reduction of construction costs, the reduction of power consumption or to enable a better facility and project management [40]. Hence, the smart building design involves new opportunities for planning, executing, operating as well as construction of digitized buildings [41].

The 'smartness' within this definition is referring to the automation or digital interconnection of devices within the building perimeter – that means the technology and interface is inherent to new capabilities by the building provided to the infrastructure, see D 8.2 of the project.

The so called 'Hardware' SBTs increase the overall capacity of the building faculties in scope and are often a precondition for installing the so called 'Software' SBT that provide operational capability and are often deployed on top of the 'Hardware' acting as runtime environment. The smartness of buildings has, as of now, become integral to the sustainability of buildings in regard to the energy efficiency (EE) and climate impact from the view of the European Commission. For many member country, like Germany, residential and commercial buildings account for up to 32 percent emission of carbon dioxide, outlining the potential for the building as a driver for climate change mitigation.

Within the SENSEI project, technology candidates were collected from energy efficiency program analyses performed in the work package 4, the guidelines to P4P programs developed in Deliverable 5.2 [42], and the consultation of involved experts. Additional technologies were extracted from the Energy Efficiency Measures (EEMs) of the SHERPA reports for the pilot buildings selected in task T5.1. The list was completed by consultation of external partner projects and independent research. Relevant data investigated for each technology included its potential value to a P4P program, its technological readiness and the so called deployability in buildings. Thus, the technologies chosen provide a proper selection of state-of-the art in science and industry.

An internal review determined the most promising and viable candidates from this list. These SBT undergo further and more thorough research into their market share, migration paths, as well as connected cost factors and legal restrictions imposed on them within the EU.

The following two tables provide an overview and short profiles of the selected technologies.

Error! Reference source not found.² is dedicated towards governing systems and system functionalities to be used in the context of smart buildings. Besides the header, there are five main fields for each entry, which aim to answer the respective questions briefly as follows:

- What is this technology installed for and how does it fulfil its purpose? What data is collected?
- How would the adaption of this technology add to a P4P plan and its goals?
- How deployable/ mature is this technology? Is it broadly accepted within the EU market? What is its market share?
- What other technologies have to already exist in the building or be installed beforehand?
- Does this technology have significant expenses for its installation or maintenance? Are there regulatory respective legal or interoperability restrictions on its usage? Does it only apply to buildings of a certain type/ occupancy profile?

Table 2 'Software' upgrades

Designation	Building Automation and Control System (BACS)
Brief description	The BACS interconnects and coordinates the control subsystems for the various domains and installations. All collected sensor data is displayed and visualised via a user interface where the desired target values can be set.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	The coordination of already existing subsystems is highly cost effective. A centralized control system is also often a requirement for participation in market oriented portfolios and energy service development (ESCOs, EPC-contracts etc.).
EU market share & technological readiness	Annual growth forecasts for the period of 2019-2024 range from 3.1 % to 4.8 %. About 50 % of new buildings link HVAC with other building services, but 75 % -- 90 % of overall building operation software sold remains server-based [2].
Required technologies	Domain specific subsystems and connected sensors, auxiliary systems (fault detection, performance evaluation etc.)
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	The data of the various subsystems has to be processed to a uniform presentation. The BACS has to be capable of two-way communication with all its subsystems.
Designation	Building Energy Management System (BEMS)
Brief description	The BEMS aggregates and regulates the building's energy consumption rates. The user can closely monitor and adjust controllable subsystems through this common interface.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	The monitoring of the separate energy consumption domains eases the settlement of EE programs without conflict to the electrification of space/water heating systems. The subsystems can incorporate the methods for the dynamic M&V of energy savings proposed in D7.1.
EU market share & technological readiness	The annual growth for the 2015-2020 period was around 22.48 % [3]. BEMS are commonly used for HVAC systems, lighting systems and asset performance optimization among others.
Required technologies	Energy meters, value actuators, interoperable subsystems of energy consuming/producing installations
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	The only variable cost factor is the installation of new interfaces for interoperability with the existing subsystems.
Designation	DHW storage management system
Brief description	The storage management system handles the charge, release and distribution for its connected DHW storage reservoir according to external signals. It can gather and relay relevant status information about the storage, such as capacity, release rate, operability, temperature etc.

Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	Scheduled pre-heating can relieve the grid during peak times.
EU market share & technological readiness	DHW storage management systems are already widely used.
Required technologies	Thermostats
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	Storage technologies are not in the focus of SENSEI.
Designation	Adaptive systems for controllable consumption devices
Brief description	A control system or aggregator can regulate the consumption rate of controllable devices in the building remotely. This enables Demand Side Management (DSM) for Demand Response (DR) or Smart Grid integration, and can be provided via a service platform. Candidate devices are electric vehicles, heat pumps, night storage heaters and electric energy storages among others.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	Controllable equipment lets building owners benefit from DR service tariffs and makes the demand prediction more resilient. Energy savings accumulated by EE improvements can be stored for later release during peak times, relieving the grid. The control systems can target deep energy retrofits.
EU market share & technological readiness	Most controllable consumption devices provide a separate management system.
Required technologies	Advanced control system (e.g., BACS/BEMS), controllable consumption devices (including batteries, TES)
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	SENSEI focusses on EE, but can utilize synergies with DR. Controllable consumption devices can be expensive in their installation.
Designation	Ventilation control system
Brief description	The room humidity and temperature are measured through air quality sensors. The ventilation activity is automatically regulated to meet the adjustable set points. An automated schedule profits from night/free cooling and H,x-directed control.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	Energy consumption at peak times can be reduced.
EU market share & technological readiness	The indoor air quality monitoring market is forecast to grow over 8 % over the 2021–2025 period [4].
Required technologies	Air quality and presence sensors, HVAC

Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	Retroactive HVAC system installation is expensive and scales with the building size.
Designation	Window control system
Brief description	Based on sunlight incidence determined by light sensors, or following a predefined schedule, insulated windows with varying spectral properties or moveable shades can automatically reduce exposition to heat radiation at peak times.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	Advanced window control systems effectively lower the energy consumption for cooling and can be coordinated with ventilation and heating systems through a BACS.
EU market share & technological readiness	For the 2018-2024 period, the market is forecast to grow at an annual rate of about 6 % due to the increasing implementation of these systems in the health care sector [5].
Required technologies	Insulated windows with varying spectral properties, moveable shades, light sensors, microprocessors
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	As a separate installation would be costly, this upgrade is most suited for combination with a general modernization of windows, or for otherwise inaccessible windows.
Designation	Participation in Smart Building communities or cooperation models
Brief description	The data BACs and BEMSs aggregate can be shared between cooperating buildings to identify opportunities to participate in energy saving portfolios and evaluate EEM plans. The energy management these control systems provide further enable the provision of EE as a demand-side resource.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	Management systems can share their accumulated data with big data collectors both as a business model to compensate for diminishing sales of energy, and for participation in social policies (e.g., addressing energy poverty). Communication interfaces also facilitate the use of EE as a demand-side grid resource / network service (e.g., avoiding congestion), or as a demand-side energy resource for the power system (e.g., investment by third parties in EE auctions).
EU market share & technological readiness	The implementation as a network service to the power system is currently deemed to have the greatest chance to be operational in the EU as the expected guarantees required from the grid operator may be less stringent, compared to capacity and data auctions.
Required technologies	Advanced control system (e.g., BACS/BEMS)
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	The energy market legislation is very restrictive in regard to demand-side energy resource provision. The P4P offer is probably not sufficiently robust yet to contractually guarantee a certain capacity.
Designation	Automated lighting system

Brief description	The lighting system can be equipped with presence and sunlight sensors to automatically adjust the local artificial lighting to the presence of occupants and natural light respectively. In addition, the system can incorporate adjustable lighting schedules.
Synergy potential (to EE specifications / P4P plans)	This energy measure can easily be incorporated into long-ranging P4P plans.
EU market share & technological readiness	The Smart Lighting Market was over USD 2 billion in 2017 and is expected to exhibit a robust annual growth of around 20 % between 2018 and 2024. Europe holds the highest share in the smart lighting market worldwide [6].
Required technologies	Sensors (motion, light)
Significant cost factors & restrictions (if any)	New outlets in places which have not been covered before

Technical installations in **Error! Reference source not found.**3 are required/desirable for some of the systems in the table above (viable pre-conditions), and/or are easily incorporable into P4P plans to achieve further alignment with the EE specifications. They are grouped by domain or functionality as those have increased the likelihood of being applicable to the same P4P programs. Most of them are widely used, with their importance mostly depending on building region (member country) and type (commercial /residential). Minor overlaps between the packages might occur but are not detrimental to the selection process.

Table 3 'Hardware' upgrades for buildings

Category	Description
Local energy generation	The inclusion of local energy generation (e.g., photovoltaic panels, (micro) wind turbines) and energy saving converters (e.g., thermal solar modules for DHW) can steer a program towards the goal of decarbonizing the power system. Renewable energy generation is, however, not at the centre of SENSEI.
Domain interlock	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems coordinate the building's installations in these domains to achieve a high indoor air quality and thermal comfort. They are well established in the industry. A Thermally Activated Building Structure (TABS) utilises the mass of a building as a buffer to the changing cooling or heating loads over the course of a day. The temperature of the slabs can be influenced by running cold or hot water through interior pipes.
Heat efficient technologies	Modern ventilation systems with installed waste heat recovery and filter technology can deliver potential energy savings of up to 20 percent. Heat exchange systems can facilitate the redirection of surplus heat to connected building blocks. In the same vein, room specific heating and automatic door closers avoid unnecessary and costly overproduction of heat for large buildings with inconsistent occupancy profiles.
Efficient lighting technologies	LEDs can achieve electricity savings of up to 80 percent compared to incandescent lamps and do not require a warm-up time before they reach full brightness as compact fluorescent lamps do. Light deflectors (e.g., mirrors) allow to "pipe" the light falling on the roof or on a wall-mounted collector to more interior spaces of the building.
Restorations	Replacing outdated facilities with energy use certified equipment is the most basic way of improving a building's EE and avoiding environmental compliance costs.

Thermal insulation	Modern windows stabilize the temperature by having a layer of gas between panes of glass act as thermal insulation. Their airtight installation can also significantly reduce the heat loss within the building envelope, while barely visible coatings on the glass reflect long-waved heat radiation. Plastic spacers have less thermal conductivity than traditional aluminium spacers. Sun protections such as window facades and solar films can provide further relieve to the cooling system.
Metering devices	Metering systems record information about the consumption, voltage level, current or similar properties of a building's installations or accumulate them for an entire building in near-real time. Smart Meters are capable of displaying these data and communicating with the consumer and the supplier in either direction. Thus they can greatly contribute to awareness in consumption as well as to monitoring and billing arrangements.
Controllable consumption devices	Devices that can be controlled remotely in their consumption/release profile through metering systems can contribute to DR services and peak load reduction. This category comprises electric vehicle chargers, heat pumps, night storage heaters and electric energy storages among others.
Frequency converters	Frequency converters can be used in the engineering building systems to optimize the operation of fans, pumps, and other relevant equipment.
Energy retrofitting technologies	Thermal Energy Storage (TES) reduces the energy consumption for heating/cooling during peak climatic conditions and makes energy savings more impactful by providing storage capacities. Geothermal heat pumps access the heat stored beneath a building to condition its interior. Rotary heat wheels and heat pipes can manage to recover 50-80 % of heat energy for redeploy in ventilation temperature regulation. Desiccant-based cooling systems for buildings with high occupancy profiles such as hospitals, supermarkets or apartment buildings can take up large dehumidification loads over long periods of time.

5.2 Application to the SENSEI models and results

Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) is a specific metric or measurement aiming to assess a certain maturity of a technology in order to enable a comparison of different technologies. The first TRL approach was designed in the 1970 by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) in order to assess the readiness of space technology [43]. Later in the mid-90s the scale has been expanded and further explained by more definitions for each level. Today, it is mainly used as an effective tool for communicating the progress and status of innovations and new technologies. The European Commission defined in total 9 TRL levels from a basic technology research up to a system test launch and operations. The higher the TRL, the more advanced and ready the technology is for large-scale use. The advantage of using TRL in SENSEI is that it enables the observation and identification of obstacles as well as uncertainties in the implementation of smart energy services [43]. Hence, the TRL assists in testing and improving for the services and data models for its efficient use in the European Building Stock. A mapping onto the TRL levels, like they are used in the H2020 program, e.g. by the commission, is possible:

Table 4 TRL levels according to EC

Technology Readiness Level	Description
TRL 1.	Basic principles observed
TRL 2.	Technology concept formulated
TRL 3.	Experimental proof of concept
TRL 4.	Technology validated in lab
TRL 5.	Technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL 6.	Technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
TRL 7.	System prototype demonstration in operational environment

TRL 8.	System complete and qualified
TRL 9.	Actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)

As described in the previous chapter, the services based on both hardware and software technologies must be dealt with in the SENSEI project. Local energy generation and flexibilities will provide business opportunities but will also need technical installation and thus, lead to integration costs mainly driven by technical problems based on interoperability. Domain convergence, like domain interlock, will cause a higher optimisation potential but cause personal data to be elicited. This involves a large number of interfaces from various vendors that must be made interoperable, which is a complex technical task that must be carefully evaluated upfront. SENSEI considered use cases on the high-level for the possible business models of the hardware and software technologies in place, looking into the overall runtime-environments and technical functions to realize P4P models. For most of those platforms, the TRL is already at a level where individual SBTs have made it to the market, thus, can be put into services.

Systems as well as base technologies must be assessed for their TRL and then be mapped onto the services to be implemented in the real operational environment. Based on the previous experience, technical standards are the way to go in order to implement the needed base-technology and services at a meaningful TRL. However, the scope of the P4P services is broad and there are a lot of systems, which need to be integrated and which are under the governance and various heterogeneous parties. This leads to a high amount of coordination even if standards are used and agreed upon upfront by the parties, e.g. based on standards maps and roadmaps as depicted in this deliverable. In order to take into account the non-functional requirements, the two most prominent are interoperability and IT-security. Here, methods like maturity models as well as domain specific analysis can help and contribute to easing the integration and planning upfront.

The following table shows the application of TRL to the services in the P4P model of the SENSEI project.

Table 5 Application of TRL to services

SERVICE	TRL
Building Automation and Control System (BACS)	7
The BACS interconnects and coordinates the control subsystems for the various domains and installations. All collected sensor data is displayed and visualised via a user interface where the desired target values can be set. Annual growth forecasts for the period of 2019-2024 range from 3.1 % to 4.8 %. About 50 % of new buildings link HVAC with other building services, but 75 % -- 90 % of overall building operation software sold remains server-based [2].	System prototype demonstration in operational environment. BACS functionalities and capabilities are already tested in operational environment, but are still newer systems, however, which are currently being further developed for widespread use.
Building Energy Management System (BEMS)	7
The BEMS aggregates and regulates the building's energy consumption rates. The user can closely monitor and adjust controllable subsystems through this common interface. The annual growth for the 2015-2020 period was around 22.48 % [3]. BEMS are commonly used for HVAC systems, lighting systems and asset performance optimization among others.	System prototype demonstration in operational environment. Various use cases for BEMS systems have been developed and tested to achieve improved reporting of energy and comfort parameters
DHW storage management system	9
The storage management system handles the charge, release and distribution for its connected DHW storage reservoir according to external signals. It can gather and relay relevant status information about the storage, such as capacity, release rate, operability, temperature etc. Scheduled pre-heating can relieve the grid during peak times.	Actual system Proven in operational environment. The DHW storage management systems are already widely used.
Adaptive systems for controllable consumption devices	9
A control system or aggregator can regulate the consumption rate of controllable devices in the building remotely. This enables Demand Side Management (DSM) for Demand Response (DR) or Smart Grid integration, and can be provided via a service platform.	The different devices mentioned are already implemented in the current energy system, as well as tested and proven in their operational environment.

<p>Candidate devices are electric vehicles, heat pumps, night storage heaters and electric energy storages among others.</p> <p>Controllable equipment lets building owners benefit from DR service tariffs and makes the demand prediction more resilient.</p>	
<p>Ventilation control system</p>	<p>8</p>
<p>The room humidity and temperature are measured through air quality sensors. The ventilation activity is automatically regulated to meet the adjustable set points. An automated schedule profits from night/free cooling and H,x-directed control.</p> <p>The indoor air quality monitoring market is forecast to grow over 8 % over the 2021–2025 period [4].</p> <p>Retroactive HVAC system installation is expensive and scales with the building size.</p>	<p>The retroactive HVAC system is complete and qualified. However, due to the high investment, they are less affordable not yet used throughout the market.</p>
<p>Window control system</p>	<p>6</p>
<p>Based on sunlight incidence determined by light sensors, or following a predefined schedule, insulated windows with varying spectral properties or moveable shades can automatically reduce exposition to heat radiation at peak times.</p> <p>For the 2018-2024 period, the market is forecast to grow at an annual rate of about 6 % due to the increasing implementation of these systems in the health care sector [5].</p> <p>As a separate installation would be costly, this upgrade is most suited for combination with a general modernization of windows, or for otherwise inaccessible windows.</p>	<p>The technology is demonstrated in the relevant environment but has not yet been rolled out over large areas. Like for the ventilation control system, the costs are too high for widespread use</p>
<p>Participation in Smart Building communities or cooperation models</p>	<p>6</p>
<p>The data BACSS and BEMSs aggregate can be shared between cooperating buildings to identify opportunities to participate in energy saving portfolios and evaluate EEM plans. The energy management these control systems provide further enable the provision of EE as a demand-side resource.</p>	<p>Participation in smart building communities and collaborative models are demonstrated in the relevant environment. However, most of these models are still in its infancy but increasingly tested with the different BEMS systems. However, regulatory issues are still open for widespread use.</p>

<p>Communication interfaces also facilitate the use of EE as a demand-side grid resource / network service (e.g., avoiding congestion), or as a demand-side energy resource for the power system (e.g., investment by third parties in EE auctions).</p> <p>The implementation as a network service to the power system is currently deemed to have the greatest chance to be operational in the EU as the expected guarantees required from the grid operator may be less stringent, compared to capacity and data auctions.</p> <p>The energy market legislation is very restrictive in regard to demand-side energy resource provision. The P4P offer is probably not sufficiently robust yet to contractually guarantee a certain capacity.</p>	
<p>Automated lighting system</p>	<p>5</p>
<p>The lighting system can be equipped with presence and sunlight sensors to automatically adjust the local artificial lighting to the presence of occupants and natural light respectively. In addition, the system can incorporate adjustable lighting schedules. This energy measure can easily be incorporated into long-ranging P4P plans. The Smart Lighting Market was over USD 2 billion in 2017 and is expected to exhibit a robust annual growth of around 20 % between 2018 and 2024. Europe holds the highest share in the smart lighting market worldwide [6].</p>	<p>Automated lightning systems will get a great impact for smart buildings and will be integrated into P4P plans. The system has already implemented some functions and has been validated in the relevant environment. It is therefore ready for demonstrative implementation in the smart building context.</p>

6 Recommendations for to data models and service interfaces used in P4P programmes

P4P programmes entail many advantages to develop tailored energy solutions for smart building stocks, which can maximize savings and financial outcomes for all involved parties. The developed business models including services and data model in the P4P programmes, can mitigate cost barriers, enable overall access to the energy market, and allows the adaption of new energy solutions. As has been described in chapter 2 of the SENSEI P4P model, the construct of a third-party bidding platform enables benefits for different parties, such as the enhancement of EE in buildings via subsidies and Energy Efficiency Obligation Schemes (EEOS), the stabilization of the grid for the DSOs or the return in investments for private investors. Therefore, the primary focus is on removing entry barriers that allow energy data to be traded and provide access to innovative and flexible services. In addition to trade between different energy companies, consumers are the main actors that are included in the P4P programs. To enable these P4P programs for all participants in the energy market, standards are inevitable. Standards are not only used for the uniform transmission of data and information, they also create quality, trust and security for all market participants.

The following key recommendations can be derived from the topic of interfaces, standardisation and regulation for the SBTs. The recommendations are designed for the users of the SBT technologies.

- Systems under various governance have to be integrated, thus, technical complexity grows and **new methods of complexity reduction** become necessary. In addition to numerous benefits and new opportunities, digitization also brings complexity to the energy transition process. This is evident in the area of flexibility and integration, their coordination and operation, where standardization and digitization are core requirements. While the problems are technically solvable, the solutions must also be scalable, expandable and maintainable. All in all, this increases the complexity for new smart building technologies.
- **Standards for interfaces must be the key** to integrate systems in time and budget. Standardization of technical interfaces and architecture management serve to manage complexity. The creation of uniform and permanent technical regulations is focused by standards and the knowledge for application is documented. Likewise, different types

of standards exist and must be taken into account – as the levels of interoperability dictate. A consistent architecture description with the necessary standards will be even more necessary in the future to create a level of exchange.

- While the technical side as well as the business model side are typically developed separate, the **concept of maturity models, such as TRL or SGIMM must be applied** to the base technology under consideration. In addition to standards, methods such as SGIMM have the potential to determine the maturity of technologies. Maturity levels are intended not only to represent the state of a technology, but also to show its development and future potential.
- As data is being exchanged and P4P markets grow, the number of market participants grow. More participants mean more **possible entry points for an (cyber) attack** as well as more interest for third parties to exploit vulnerabilities. Per se, an evaluation of the system can be done by SGIS-SL analysis form EC mandate M/490. However, this must be constantly adopted to the criticality of the overall P4P market for the electric energy supply as a whole.
- The **Data protection level** of the data being exchanged must be monitored and checked for according to GDPR. Also, there is a method available to do a fully integrated evaluation of this. Aspects of IT security are essential to mitigate attack points and reduce vulnerability. The security of the overall system is paramount and must be maintained for security of supply.
- Finally, the fallacy of a chicken-egg problem must be taken into consideration. Markets do not evolve because technical solutions fitting perfectly are **missing and costs for integration and ramp-up** could be too high. However, insights on requirements for standards must be derived from practice, thus, the new market models contribute to better standards. Later adopters will benefit from this mechanism.

A maturity analysis of the services that are offered on the third-party bidding platform is recommended. There are various methods for determining the maturity level, such as the classic TRL model, in which the services can be examined in their technical development. In addition to the technical progress of the services, development trends are also examined, and processes and properties are optimized. Maturity studies also offer opportunities to compare the services of different providers on such platforms. The development of data models can also be examined with the help of maturity levels. Maturity levels can support application development during

data modelling in P4P programs. Particularly in the area of smart building stock applications, data management is often still at a lower maturity level and development stage as various standardization cases and use cases are still pending and need to be worked out. Data models and standardization in the smart building stock should therefore develop in the further process at the maturity level in the direction of implementation. Maturity models can be used not only to indicate the achievement of various KPIs for the deployment of the technologies, but they can also indicate statements about the quality of implementation as well as possible paths for implementation.

Another focal point for the recommendation is the inclusion of various standards for smart building stocks. On the one hand, standardization provides the framework for the services and data models; on the other hand, it creates interoperability and enables a connection of new and future actors to such a third-party bidding platform. Especially in the face of increasing complexity due to more heterogeneous actors and associated different systems, standards will become ever more indispensable in the future so that common services and data models can be used across several organizations.

In addition to standardization, the legal framework with regard to compliance with the GDPR is also necessary. It is recommended to consider the topics legally in order to ensure proper handling of personal data.

The following recommendations are offered for the SDOs standardizing interfaces for P4P solutions. The recommendations are designed for the users of the SBT technologies.

- Dedicated examination of new markets and use cases will be beneficial to properly map and understand requirements towards technical solutions for the technical committees dealing with electric energy and flexibility markets.
- Use cases from research projects should be collected, meta-data should be added and classification is needed. This will lead to re-usable knowledge for future projects and, thus, solve problems and challenges imposed to implement SBTs.

The recommendations support to ensure that SBTs are implemented according to the legal regulations and the associated standards. The SBTs development is verified with the help of maturity models. These steps are necessary to develop reliable and secure SBTs whose implementation is verified.

7 Conclusion

The present report shows the interfaces of data models and smart services to improve the Energy Efficiency of the European Building Stock, presenting a compiled stack of possible and useful Smart Services (and technologies). It is important to distinguish between hardware and software technology stacks. The technologies presented are the result of a desk research and their characteristics are described in context with the building types in SENSEI and put into simulation.

The deliverable started with a short overview of the SENSEI P4P model and a list of relevant standards that are needed for the SENSEI P4P model. In chapter 4, the two main concepts of the deliverable have been introduced, namely the Smart Grid Interoperability Maturity Model (SGIMM) and the Smart Grid information security and privacy method (SGIS). The SGIMM aimed at achieving interoperability within and between Smart Grid stakeholders. The SGIMM offered guidance for improving interoperability at the community or national level, assessed interoperability progress in the Smart Grid community and encouraged an interoperability-aware culture with individual and shared roadmaps for improvement. The different levels of the method provided the basis for the assessment of the interoperability evaluation in the scope of smart building technologies.

The Smart Grid information security and privacy methods (SGIS) as well as the associated data protection and privacy (DPP) enabled that the collection, utilization, processing, storage, transmission of data and ensured that all information from the participating actors will be protected. The Smart Grid services were proposed to be used in a system that is inherently secure by design within the critical infrastructure of transmission and distribution networks, as well as within the connected properties. The security levels that were established in the model provided information of which level of security can be determined for each component layer.

The elaborated concepts were finally tailored and applied to the SENSEI models. First, the smart building technologies in the P4P. The tables provided an overview and short profiles of the selected technologies. **Error! Reference source not found.**² was dedicated towards governing systems and system functionalities to be used in the context of smart buildings. In total, eight smart grid building technologies were introduced and analysed according to different factors. In the step, the different technology services were analysed according to their maturity in the smart grid.

From this evaluation, various recommendations were derived for the use of smart building technologies in the energy market. The recommendation considered different aspects. On the one hand, recommendations are given on how to deal with complexity. Standards are a key to the interoperable integration of different systems. These must be documented and applied between the heterogeneous players. To enable these P4P programs for all participants in the energy market, standards are inevitable. Standards are not only used for the uniform transmission of data and information, they also create quality, trust and security for all market participants. In addition to standards, maturity models are also needed to assess and evaluate the maturity of technologies. Possible cyber-attacks must also be averted with a secure IT system. SGIS offers an effective concept for this by defining different data protection classes.

Thus, contributions of “technology packages” for building for P4P were evaluated and conclusions drawn. The basic concepts listed in this document intended to provide initial pointers for secure and interoperable integration of the various technologies into the Smart Grid. These conclusions put an emphasis on certain combinations of stacks, which provide better revenue and smartness than others.

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